

Eyes in the Skin I Live In: The Incorporation of Surveillance in Mediatized Culture

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Abstract

Increasing biotechnological interventions to the human body challenge long-established Western binaries, opening up a political struggle over the boundaries they cut through. While this incorporated technology enhances and extends human lives, it can also facilitate (self-)surveillance, especially when it involves information technology capable of generating, analyzing and sharing data. At this confluence of human and nonhuman, the article explores the polysemy of technologized skin through Pedro Almodóvar's film *The Skin I Live In* (2011) and Michel Foucault's notion of "technologies" by which humans are made subjects. The complex system of power in this film is compellingly figured in the protagonist Vera's transgenic skin, leading us to regard the skin itself as "eyes", that is, a (self-)surveillance so pervasive that it disappears from our conscious register. The contrast between Vera's flawless transgenic skin and the apotropaic "worn" skin-space she creates—the conspicuous patchwork seams and shadowy wall markings—highlights the incorporated surveillance in de-corporalized society, while at the same time suggesting potential strategies to live through today's complex system of existence.

Keywords: body modification, transhuman, power, self-fashioning, new materialism

The opening scene of Pedro Almodóvar's film *The Skin I Live In* (2011) overlooks the city of Toledo, Spain. The camera zooms in on a magnificent cloistered mansion, El Cigarral, swiftly scanning its layers of incarceration and surveillance: home security system, fences, walls, grids, and a locked room inside. On the stark white walls of this brightly lit modernist room are bulging glass eyes—dome-shaped surveillance cameras—watching every movement by Vera, the lone inmate. Vera is held captive by Robert Ledgard, a pioneering plastic surgeon, who has been

secretly experimenting on her for the last six years. In his private medical laboratory and operating theater within the mansion, Ledgard has replaced her entire skin with a transgenic one named "Gal", after his dead wife. With the hardness of pig hide and insect exoskeleton engineered into human cells, the artificial skin is resistant to burns and insect bites, yet still sensitive to the touch. Besides Ledgard, Vera's contact with the outside world is limited to the housekeeper Marilia, via either an intercom or a dumbwaiter through which she is provided with food, books, and other objects. In this panoptic space, Vera waits—making patchwork sculptures, inscribing on the wall, and practicing yoga—for an escape. The surveillance cameras project black-and-white images onto screens in the kitchen that Marilia monitors, and also high-definition colour images onto a large screen in Ledgard's room, adjacent to Vera's. The screen allows Ledgard to zoom in and scrutinize Vera's skin, face, and body. When Vera's magnified face stares back at the camera, it is clear that she is aware of a certain power she holds over Ledgard. Sensing his narcissistic pride as a seemingly omnipotent plastic surgeon, she starts to act as if she has developed Stockholm syndrome, and this flusters Ledgard. This subtle shift in their power relation is radically accelerated when Marilia's villainous son Zeca violently irrupts into the tightly controlled setting, triggering a series of flashbacks.

Twelve years earlier, Ledgard's wife Gal suffers severe burns in a car accident while running away with Zeca. With Ledgard's obsessive care, Gal survives. However, upon accidentally seeing her disfigured skin reflected in a windowpane, she throws herself out of the window. The suicide is witnessed by the couple's daughter Norma, leaving her traumatized. Six years later, grown into a naïve teenager and having made a modest recovery, Norma accompanies her father to a wedding reception, where she is attracted by a young man, Vincente. As they attempt to have sex, Norma starts to scream in panic, and Vincente runs away. Shortly after being hospitalized for severe social anxiety, Norma kills herself by jumping out of a window. The vindictive Ledgard kidnaps Vincente and performs vaginoplasty on him on the day of Norma's funeral. From this point on, Ledgard methodically takes apart Vincente's body and puts it back together as Vera, through numerous invasive surgeries, skin grafts and hormone medications. For Vincente/Vera, then, beyond the architectural confines, the transgenic skin itself is a "cruel, ingenious cage" (Foucault 1980, 148), a prison and a clinic "to carry out experiments, to alter behaviour, to train or correct individuals" (Foucault 1995, 203). Back in the present day, having learned that Ledgard has engineered her as a simulacrum of his lost wife, Vera performs as if she

is fully conforming to the imposed identity.¹ Ledgard, outplayed, trusts Vera and hopes to live with her, as a couple. No longer confined to her room, Vera seizes the earliest opportunity to kill Ledgard, and escapes the mansion (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Screenshot from Pedro Almodóvar, *The Skin I Live In* (2011) © [El Deseo] 0:01:09

Skin/Technology/Power

As the site where constant negotiations of what is me and not-me take place, the skin is a metonym for human life that is fundamentally integrated into the material, social, cultural, and political realms. Every thing and every individual emerges, evolves, and passes away "by incorporating, and being incorporated into, other evolving structures that suffuse it" (Crary and Kwinter 1992, 12–14). The increasingly blurred boundary between the biological and the technological, however, renders the term "incorporation" more literal than ever. Although human bodies have long been extended by prostheses, biotechnological interventions into the body are generating both new hopes and new anxieties. Against this backdrop, many areas of creative practice take the technologized body as a vehicle to interrogate contemporary subjectivity. Collaborations between art and science in the domain of bio-art, for example, critique practices such as cloning, gene therapies, and assisted reproductive technologies; and artistic projects that use skin, tissue cultures, or transgenesis as their main medium reflect on what it is to be human in

the era of biotechnological intervention (Kellett 2018). As the restless site where boundaries between the biological and the mechanical, subject and object, creator and created may be made or breached, the skin is an effective device for exploring traditional Western categories and postulating the consequences of ethically charged scientific procedures (Squier 2004, 10).

This essay explores the polysemy of technologized skin at the confluence of the human and nonhuman, through the cinematic narrative of *The Skin I Live In* (2011). The incorporation of technology in this film is so naturalized that it goes beyond being "skinlike", and actually becomes skin. I liken this thoroughgoing incorporation to the equally ubiquitous contemporary surveillance and juxtapose the technologized skin with a contrasting type of human-nonhuman confluence achieved via *everyday material contacts*. The protagonist Vera's flawless transgenic skin is particularly unsettling when placed next to the conspicuous patchwork seams and wall markings she makes. The contrast draws attention to the digital transgenesis that the skin underwent during the film's postproduction process (Marcantonio 2015), and the way social media is saturated with photoshopped selfies. The dissolving body in our increasingly mediatized culture appears to be delaminated into the multiple surfaces of cyberspace (Teyssot 1994, 10), while the data gathered from our digital communications are being put together as "data doubles" and manipulated by surveillance regimes (Haggerty and Ericson 2000). Interpreted in the context of (self-)surveillance via smart technology and online communications, the complex power relation between the two protagonists of the film—the Ledgard-Vera dyad—may reveal potential strategies to work the trap we are already in.

In the following section, I examine the incorporation of technology into the human body and other everyday surfaces such as clothing, interiors, architecture, and the urban environment. With the increasing merging between the body and informatics, the skin in particular becomes a source of knowledge that supports state, corporate, and self-surveillance, challenging individual freedom and privacy. Following Michel Foucault's analysis of power, I explore Vera's situation as the incorporation, rather than internalization, of power: the complex layers of surveillance in the film are most compellingly figured in Vera's transgenic skin, leading me to consider the skin itself as "eyes", that is, as a surveillance so pervasive that it disappears from our conscious register, but fundamentally shapes our subjectivity. The idea of the skin as inspecting and disciplining eyes implies the loss of the personal in the face of "Big Other", that is, the system of surveillance capitalism (Zuboff 2015; 2016).

I then go on to consider different power relations that appear in the film, through Foucault's ideas of "technologies of power" and "technologies of the self". If power relations always exist in human relations, as Foucault suggests, what types of power might exist in human-nonhuman relations? The power relations figured in various types of "skin" that surround the two main characters highlight the importance of material interactions in the formation of human subjectivity. By placing Ledgard's transgenic skin Gal (a result of his humanist attitude) against Vera's alternative skin (the conspicuous patchwork seams and shadowy wall markings), I interpret Foucault's analysis of power from a less anthropocentric point of view.

In the final section, I examine the building blocks of Vera's architecture of resistance, which allow her to evade Ledgard's control and avoid becoming a docile body. Vera's resistance strategies are here aligned with "technologies of the self" and "self-fashioning". As Vera works the trap she is in by building affinities with the various skins she wears, I emphasize nonhuman material agency and explore the circumstances that make such agency possible. Floating between the polarities of male and female, natural and artificial, imposition and volition, Vera portrays contemporary subjectivities living with physically and digitally negotiated membranes (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Screenshot from Pedro Almodóvar, *The Skin I Live In* (2011) © [El Deseo] 1:36:10

Incorporation of power: the panoptic skin

Being habituated to everyday material objects involves a process of incorporation. Human technologies such as clothes, cars, and computers become incorporated into our lives as we merge with them almost unconsciously. Invaded and reshaped by transgenic skin, drugs, and body sculpture, Vera's cyborgian reality (Haraway 1991) leads us to probe the binary distinction between human and nonhuman, especially in the process of incorporating tools and technology. Anne Farren and Andrew Hutchison (2004) suggest that humans are now evolving from a "garment cyborg" (from the French *garnir*, "to equip"), extended by clothes, credit cards, or mobile phones, into a "flesh cyborg" whose bodies are embedded with digital, bio-, or nanotechnology that selectively activates everyday biomechanisms. Such flesh cyborgs are often imagined in creative spheres: in Robert J. Sawyer's *Hominids* (2002), implants embedded under the skin are powered by blood flow (Honeywell 2015); artist Lucy McRae's "swallowable parfum" takes the form of a cosmetic pill—the perfume is then excreted through perspiration, rendering the wearer's body into "a sort of atomizer" (van den Berg 2014). In actuality, research into creating smart skins that include display screens is well underway (Feltman 2016); implanting electronic devices into the skin for identification, law enforcement, medical history, or medications has become possible; 3D-printed electronic tattoos can help wounds heal or detect blood glucose levels (Cuthbertson 2018). As in the case of organ transplantation or mediated reproduction, human bodily functions can be extended with ingestible pharmaceuticals that aid memory, concentration, and mood (Bostrom 2005, 10–11). In this transhuman condition, technological extensions to the body become normalized, allowing all-encompassing surveillance to penetrate the human body.

Such "invisible" incorporations of technology are key to the paradigm of "ubiquitous computing," which has already infiltrated everyday life in developed countries. Technology is increasingly becoming skinlike, as with the "intelligent" skin of the built environment (Wigginton and Harris 2002, 44); smart fabric as an active membrane (Küchler 2008); smart devices that fully conform to the wearer's body (Fleischman 2016); and smart clothing such as Jacquard by Google. Embedded in the fabric of the everyday, such skinlike smart mediatic environments are capable of constantly generating data and processing information from the tiniest nuances of our intimate lives. Edward Snowden revealed in 2013 that "state surveillance had infiltrated the fabric of everyday digital communications, piggybacking on commercial

telecommunications platforms that we all use" (Bakir 2017, 2). This condition is intensified by the public "sharing and watching themselves through selfies, social media postings and biometrics such as wearable devices" (Bakir 2017, 2). Wearable digital self-tracking devices are designed to continuously monitor the wearer's health and lifestyle details such as bodily movements, heart rate, perspiration, respiration, sleep quality and quantity, activity levels, and location. Accompanying mobile device applications facilitate the analysis and sharing of these voluntarily offered personal data which are then extracted and commodified, blurring the boundary between the watcher and the watched (Lupton 2013, 394; Galič et al. 2016, 29–30).

The recent iterations of the Apple Watch (series 4 and 5) are equipped with a heart sensor that can administer a medically accurate electrocardiogram (BoF 2018), shedding fresh light on the question socialist historian E. P. Thompson (1967, 57) posed about the conditions of working life in industrial capitalism: "When the watch is worn about the neck it lies in proximity to the less regular beating of the heart. ... [How] far did it influence the inward apprehension of time of working people?" Whereas the automation of the Industrial Revolution replaced the human body with machines for more continuity and control, with smart information technology, "automation simultaneously generates information that provides a deeper level of transparency to activities that had been either partially or completely opaque", making them more easily shareable (Zuboff 2015, 76). In surveillance capitalism, which aims to predict and modify detailed nuances of our behavior as a means to produce revenue and market control (Zuboff 2015, 75; Zuboff 2016), power is identified with the ownership of information and the means of *behavioral modification* (Zuboff 2015, 82). As Shoshana Zuboff (2015, 84–85) points out, the invisible network of data capturing devices today provides the "eyes and ears" of a "world-spanning living organism" that she calls "Big Other". Our intimate quotidian realities, monitored and sold by companies such as Google or Facebook, are also made available to political institutions, building affective experiences into specific political figures (Anderson and Harrison 2010, 11; Chen 2018). Operating in the precognitive realm, surveillance becomes normalized and habitualized, that is, skinlike. Vera's superskin illustrates this datafication of the everyday via invisible and distributed sensing systems, intensified by the fact that for Vera, made radically strange and alien, forgetting about her skin is a privilege. Vera's skin reveals the unsettling power of surveillance capitalism, in which "habitats inside and outside the human body are saturated with data and produce radically distributed opportunities for observation, interpretation, communication, influence,

prediction, and ultimately modification of the totality of action; there is no escape from Big Other." (Zuboff 2015, 82) A sensorized environment, such as the Internet of Things, can scale up the "attack surface" for any cyberattack (Chui 2015), further jeopardizing individual assets and privacy. With the internet considered by many to be a fundamental right (BBC 2010), surveillance is thoroughly incorporated into contemporary life, omnipresent and inescapable, just like the skin Vera has to live in. The Vera-Ledgard dyad in the film seems to probe how individual rights are affected by surveillance capitalism, and how subjectivities are shaped by normative constraints imposed by the social media platforms through which we perform and watch each other. This situation mirrors Michel Foucault's (1995, 217) comment on surveillance society in *Discipline and Punish*, first published in 1975:

[T]he circuits of communication are the supports of an accumulation and a centralization of knowledge ... [T]he individual is carefully fabricated in [our social order], according to a whole technique of forces and bodies. [We are ...] in the panoptic machine, invested by its effects of power, which we bring to ourselves since we are part of its mechanism.

Although recent studies on surveillance have turned away from panopticism in an attempt to understand the complexities of contemporary surveillance (for example, Lyon 2006; Haggerty and Ericson 2000), the film seems to present this model as an effective metaphor for explaining "the circulation of effects of power through progressively finer channels, gaining access to individuals themselves, to their bodies, their gestures and all their daily actions" (Foucault 1980: 151–152). Jeremy Bentham's (1995, 35–36) panopticon is an architectural principle that represents the relations of power. It reduces the mechanism of power to a simple and ideal form: the inspector's lodge occupies the center of a circular building; occupying the circumference are the individual cells, each with an iron grating. Because the windows of the lodge are equipped with blinds, the persons in the cells cannot know if the inspector is absent or present.² This setup makes the persons to be inspected feel that they are under constant inspection, even though that should not be the case (Bentham 1995, 91). The mechanism assures the automatic functioning of power, that is, the inmates are "caught up in a power situation of which they are themselves the bearers" (Foucault 1995, 201).

Foucault describes a fully panoptic society as a society in which disciplinary norms have become so thoroughly integrated that they are not experienced as coming from outside (Sanders 2017, 54). Vera's skin draws attention to contemporary society as a fully panoptic one, in which the popularity of self-monitoring apps, wearable devices, and social networking platforms unwittingly exacerbates state, corporate, and self-surveillance. Foucault (1980, 154–155) refers to this integration of power as "interiorization"—the individual under the inspecting gaze will eventually interiorize it to the point that they exercise this surveillance over, and against, themselves (Foucault 1995, 202). Taking this idea further, Judith Butler (1990, 134–135) suggests that when disciplined bodies are compelled to signify the prohibitive law as their very essence and style, that law is not internalized but *incorporated*. Although the panoptic penal system may slacken its direct hold on the body and work instead on the thoughts and inclinations of the individual, it is ultimately the body that gradually incorporates the power: the style of the disciplined body is that of a branded person.

To achieve this automatic function of power, Ledgard's panopticon is constructed of multiple layers. The 24/7 surveillance maintains a hold on Vera's body within the physical structure and prevents her from violating the newly grafted skin. She is imprisoned within Ledgard's high-definition CCTV screen as a virtuality of his dead wife. She is also trapped, like a chimaera, within the technologized skin and the artificially imposed gender. Within this panopticon, the power is incorporated into Vera's body. The centrality of the transgenic skin for understanding Ledgard's obsessive control over Vera leads me to conflate the multiple layers and imagine the skin as constantly surveilling "eyes".³ Vera's skin appears to merge the watcher and the watched, linking pervasive surveillance with the culture of self-monitoring on the digital screens of mobile devices. Almodóvar, however, leaves the viewer puzzled as to what has become of the self that inhabits the immaculate skin (Fend 2017, 6). The film complexifies the actual state of incorporation in Vera, challenging the dualistic idea of "the soul trapped in a body", as well as any clear distinction between inside and outside, between male and female. Vera's radical transformation through surgical interventions and hormonal therapies, albeit forced, dispels the myth of the authentic self, and turns the viewers' attention away from the notion of identity in favor of affinities (*affinitas*, "bordering-on") (Haraway 1991). The film unfolds as Vera strategically transgresses Ledgard's power by uniquely incorporating various material surfaces

within his panopticon. Ultimately, Vera seems to emerge as *multiplicities* achieved through her affinities with her surroundings via contacts, contagions, and contaminations (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Screenshot from Pedro Almodóvar, *The Skin I Live In* (2011) © [El Deseo] 0:02:17

Relations of power

The vectors of power in the Ledgard-Vera dyad are thus concentrated on the various types of "skin" (the transgenic skin, Vera's wall, clothing, the surfaces of objects, the screens), estranging the naturalized process of material and social incorporation that constitutes subjectivity. Power here has its principle in a "*concerted distribution* of bodies, surfaces, lights, gazes; in an arrangement whose internal mechanisms produce the relation in which individuals are caught up" (Foucault 1995, 202. my emphasis). In this regard, it is useful to consider Foucault's "technologies of power" and "technologies of the self" alongside each other to understand human relationships—and by implication, human-nonhuman relationships—in the film. Although Foucault's analysis of power formations is widely regarded as anthropocentric (see, for example, Barad 2007), it frequently emphasizes how power functions via arrangements of various elements including nonhumans, somewhat mirroring Deleuze and Guattari's idea of "assemblage"; for instance, the prison environment and its very materiality are an instrument and

vector of power in creating docile bodies (Foucault 1995, 30, 202; See also Lemke 2015: 12–13).⁴

Foucault's (1997, 225) idea of technology implies a certain modification of individuals, in the sense of acquiring skills and attitudes. Technologies of power aim to determine others' conduct and submit them to certain ends; and technologies of the self are the operations on our own bodies, thoughts, and ways of being so as to transform, and gain knowledge about, ourselves. The two are closely interlinked, because power relations are present in any human interaction and are something to be carefully managed so as to avoid a state of "domination" (Foucault et al. 1987, 114). Foucault is careful to distinguish power relations (strategic games between *liberties*) and "the states of domination" in which all reversibility of power is blocked (Foucault et al. 1987, 130). To minimize domination, individuals must acquire techniques of the self and practice the ethics of self-fashioning (Foucault et al. 1987, 130). It would seem that the shift of Foucault's focus from technologies of power and domination ("earlier Foucault") to technologies of the self and discourse on ethics ("second Foucault") may not be a split or divide in his thinking, as it is often received (see for example Braidotti 2007). It is instead a *continuation* of his lifelong project to rethink the subject, via adopting a less dualistic and more relational approach, emphasizing how care for the self is also care for others, effectively recoding *disciplines as techniques of the self*, and placing disciplines in a relationship to freedom and liberty (Osborne 2015, 27; see also Foucault 1983: 208–209).⁵

Appearing in *The Skin I Live In* are different types of power relations, and Ledgard and Vera exercise contrasting technologies of power. Ledgard's dualist attitude requires a clear subject-object divide, blocking reciprocity in his relation to people and things—"command on one side and subjection on the other" (Bentham 1995, 90). Vera, on the other hand, adopts "technologies of the self" as modalities of becoming, refashioning herself in response to Ledgard's mechanism of power. It is the crisis of Vera's self that drives her to seek alternative methods of subjectivation.⁶ Self-fashioning was Foucault's response to the crisis of self, brought on by "the death of God" (Nietzsche) and "the death of man" (Foucault et al. 1987; Milchman and Rosenberg 2007, 45, 51). After a chain of circumstances following the secularization—the scientific exploitation of humans for social control, fascism, and biopolitics—the West lost faith in the "authentic subject" (Milchman and Rosenberg 2007, 48–49). As a response to this loss of the authentic subject, Foucault suggests self-fashioning as a technique through which you *create*

your own self, taking your life and body as the material for a work of art (Milchman and Rosenberg 2007, 56–57, 60).

If this "art" can be understood as "a way of being or of acting" (Partridge 2006, 148), Vera's art is diametrically opposed to Ledgard's. Vera's *pièce de résistance* is the alternative skin that she acquires by building affinities with her living environment through marking and touching. This unique skinspace is constantly threatened by Ledgard's Vicente-Vera transition project, which is most strikingly figured in the transgenic skin. Almodóvar presents Vera as Ledgard's "art" by drawing viewers' attention to the Titians adorning his mansion—the *Venus of Urbino* (Uffizi) and *Venus with an Organist and a Dog* (Prado)—and the copy of *The Selfish Gene* (Richard Dawkins, 1976)⁷ on his bedside table, before letting Vera appear on a high-definition surveillance screen in a pose similar to the Titian Venus. This camerawork links Vera with a long line of humanoid automata, marvelous artifices against nature. Our fascination with enlivened simulacra—Pygmalion's statue, Hoffmann's Olympia, Villiers de L'Isle-Adam's Andréide (from the French, *androïde*), Fritz Lang's robot in *Metropolis* (1927), the replicant in *Blade Runner*, Ava in *Ex Machina*—reveals age-old myths of man as God (Camille 1989, 250). Ledgard's "art" demonstrates the human tendency to reshape the world according to our own needs (Lemma 2012, 1292), while reminding us of the tragic sequence of hubris-nemesis-catastrophe (Gell 1996, 29). Ledgard's attitude towards Vera as the transparent object of his art/science reveals the type of technique of power he exercises (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Screenshot from Pedro Almodóvar, *The Skin I Live In* (2011) © [El Deseo] 0:08:31

Almodóvar seems to align the superskin Gal with transparent glass surfaces that embody Ledgard's extropian attitude. As Ledgard creates the artificial skin in his laboratory, impeccably smooth surfaces fill the screen: gleaming and transparent petri dishes, test tubes, glass walls, all meticulously maintained without the trace of a fingerprint. Along with Vera's brightly lit modernist room, Ledgard's glass laboratory is a space that craves total visibility and fears darkened spaces. Vera's skin is "transparent" to Ledgard, who controls and experiments with it as a value-neutral tool for scientific knowledge. The panopticon was the architectural formula for "power through transparency", for subjection by illumination (Foucault 1980, 154). Foucault (1980, 152–153) aligns this formula with the late eighteenth-century Rousseauist dream of a transparent society, which aimed to eliminate any shadowy areas where arbitrary political acts, religious superstitions, or tyrannical plots might be fomented. If Bentham's dream was embodied in panoptic systems, then in modernist architectural discourse Le Corbusier, Mies van der Rohe, and others upheld the technological and ideological virtues of the transparent glass wall (Vidler 2003, 3–4). More than fifty years on, glass architecture was criticized in Paul Virilio's (1991; 2002) works on cybernetic space and time: with the proliferation of cameras and detectors along with transparent building materials, the ancient private-public occultation gave way to an overriding state of overexposure (Virilio 1991, 11–13). This overexposure through immanent cameras offers a world in which there is no secrecy or privacy, no shadowy area to hide or conceal (Virilio 1991, 19). Although the transparency of modernist glass architecture seems to have given way to skinlike translucency in the contemporary built environment (Riley 1995), it is the radically distributed sensing system that renders any physical structure transparent. The "intelligent" skin of buildings with omnipresent sensors seems to actualize the Rousseauist dream today—and can be experienced through Vera's skin.

What is lost in the glass architecture is "the rightful feeling of possession, of the ownership of objects that are extensions of ourself" (Teyssot 2012, 148). Surrealist critic Roger Caillois (1984, 23) emphasizes such affinities in his idiosyncratic study of insect psychasthenia: the insects' skin changes as they come into contact with their surroundings, forming a "mutual organization" or "reciprocal topography". Their pure fascination with space becomes literally *incorporated*. Through the insects' play with their surroundings, Caillois underscores our mimetic relationship to the world, with the skin as the place where boundary negotiations take place (Benthien 2002, ix). The inverse of Caillois's scenario appears in Aziz + Cucher's *Interiors*

(1998–2000). This time, the space copies the skin of its conspicuously absent dweller, who seems to have been absorbed into the modernist architecture (Katz-Freiman 2002). The walls of the space resemble human skin, complete with pimples, pores, and freckles. The game of power between a space and its inhabitants in Caillois has turned into a state of domination in *Interiors*, which becomes even more sinister in its animated version *Passage* (2002), as the skin-walls appear to breathe. This dystopian human-architecture hybrid seems to articulate the implications of biotechnology for the human condition (Katz-Freiman 2002), in the face of the type of science Ledgard conducts (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Screenshot from Pedro Almodóvar, *The Skin I Live In* (2011) © [El Deseo] 0:10:33

Vera's architecture of resistance: patchwork scars and tattooed walls

Foucault (1989, 224) asserts that where there is a power relation, there is the possibility of resistance. Following this, Denis Hollier (1993, x–xi) asks: if the panopticon is an architecture that shapes matter and produces subjects, if it is a system for institutionalization, why would architectural devices not work in reverse? By frequently juxtaposing Vera's skin with the white walls of her cell, Almodóvar seems to equate these traceless surfaces with Ledgard's suffocating control and surveillance, while simultaneously offering the surfaces as alternative skins through which Vera may constitute her new self. As she lives in a foreign skin that neither she nor passing time can mark, her way of working Ledgard's power is to mark the material surfaces in

her immediate environment. When the dumbwaiter delivers feminine dresses and makeup materials, Vera rips the dresses to pieces and then puts them back together to cover various surfaces in her room. She uses the makeup materials to write and draw on the wall. Both acts can be seen as a process of making her own self, skin, and body within and beyond the control of Ledgard's panopticon. Vera thus builds her architecture of resistance by fashioning herself through "wearing" (in its double senses) all the imposed surfaces she can touch, turning them into inhabitable spheres. Just as many species of animal mark their territory via sensorial touch, wearing may also be humans' way of creating a home. As Vera wears the space, she is worn by it. Animated by its constant "overlap" with Vera, her space articulates the idea of reciprocal belonging between a place and its inhabitant (Sloterdijk 2005). The dwelling and the dweller form a collective organism—or rather, a "common skin,"—to apply psychoanalyst Didier Anzieu's (1989) notion of the Skin Ego.

Anzieu suggests the Skin Ego as the psychological boundary of self that is continuously remade through sensorial, material, and embodied contact. The establishment of a flexible boundary of self starts with the mother's holding and handling touch, experienced on the baby's skin. Anzieu (1989, 62–63) explains the formation and function of the Skin Ego ("the phantasy of a common skin") thus:

[The feedback between the baby and its mothering environment] leads to the eventual constitution of an interface, imagined as a skin common to both mother and child, an interface which has the mother on one side and the child on the other. ... Connecting them as it does, this common skin ensures direct communication between the two partners, reciprocal empathy and an adhesive identification: it is a unique screen which comes to resonate with the sensations, emotions, mental images and vital rhythms of the two.

This interface gradually transforms into an increasingly open system, so that the two can function independently (Anzieu 1989, 63). Its function of *registering* tactile sensory traces includes *nonhuman material* contact as an integral part of building a flexible boundary of the self:

This function of the Skin-ego develops on a dual basis, biological and social. Biologically, the first pattern of reality is imprinted on the skin; socially, the individual who belongs to a particular social group is marked by cuts, scarification, skin-painting, tattoos, make-up, hairstyles, and the supplementary layer of clothing. The Skin-ego is the original parchment that acts as a palimpsest, preserving the crossed-out, scratched-through, over-written drafts of an "original" pre-verbal writing made of traces on the skin. (Anzieu 2016, 114)⁸

The Skin Ego can then be considered as the self-in-progress made through wearing the body and other surfaces as extension of the self. The skin, which incorporates material and social relations, is a potential site for refashioning the self within those relations. Vera's wish to circumvent the loss of her skin, gender, and freedom coalesces on the surface of the walls she marks and the objects she makes. Because Vera's skin cannot register the "e-motion-ality" of touch (Barad 2012, 209), she acquires a Skin Ego via the alternative skins she creates. These surfaces stand in for her lost skin, estranging the everyday surfaces we tend to overlook. She is born out of the surfaces she wears, showing that humans are "an effect of the space they create" (Sloterdijk 2009, 1).

Almodóvar ensures that the camera shows the fresh scars on Vera's newly grafted skin in close-up before he transposes those scars onto the seams of the tight body stockings she is ordered to wear to mold the new skin. These seams reflect the technological interventions that Vera's body has undergone, not just the skin grafts, but also gender reassignment through medications and invasive surgeries. The costume also alludes to Fritz Lang's robot in *Metropolis*, pointing to the vulnerable boundary between the "natural" and the artificial broached by the transgenic body (Almodóvar, quoted in Snead 2011). The body stockings cover her entire bodily surface, including fingers and toes, functioning as yet another tool for discipline, control, and isolation. The tightness of the body stocking is aligned with the claustrophobic atmosphere created by CCTV cameras and the hypervisuality of surveillance screens. This tool for engineering the Vincente-Vera transition is a part of Ledgard's operation of power, just as the uniform is a prison authority's tool for creating docile bodies. In turn, inmates' resistance to authority—their refusal to internalize the power—often manifests in the refusal, manipulation, or deformation of the uniform. For instance, during the blanket protests in the Maze prison

(Northern Ireland, 1976–1981), to refuse to put on a prison uniform was to refuse to enter the prison system (Purbrick 2009, 16) (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Screenshot from Pedro Almodóvar, *The Skin I Live In* (2011) © [El Deseo] 0:30:35

Ledgard's power seems to be eroded, bit by bit, each time Vera rips the feminine dresses into tiny fragments. As pointed out above, Vera's self-fashioning as resistance may be understood through the hand-sewn patchwork bodies and objects she makes using the ripped fabric fragments. The fact that she puts on the dresses on over the body stocking first, before ripping them, is significant. For film theorist Tarja Laine (2014), this elaborate process of mutilating dresses evokes the sensation that Vera is cutting her own skin. The mutilation of the skin paradoxically can be a means "by which an individual endeavours to maintain body boundaries and self-cohesion" (Barrie M. Biven, quoted in Connor 2004, 57). Psychoanalyst Alexandra Lemma (2010, 15) therefore suggests that direct inscription on the skin, such as tattooing or self-cutting, needs to be seen as "figuration" rather than "disfiguration" of the body. Vera's subversive use of the dresses can be seen as an active response to a crisis of the self, an attempt to "put together" her own self. Her self-cohesion is thus achieved through wearing the alternative surfaces, giving a spatial form to what happens to her body and psyche. The patchwork heads and bodies are inspired by Louise Bourgeois's sculptures, often incorporated in her *Cell* series. Composed of everyday objects that are familiar to our bodies and experience, such as beds,

chairs, and clothes, each iteration of the *Cell* series alludes to a space "formatted by the inhabitants" (Sloterdijk 2005, 232). Bourgeois chose the name *Cell* for its polysemy—a prison cell, a monk's cell, and the smallest biological units of the body (Crone and Graf Schaesberg 2011, 85–86)—all of which correspond to Vera's environment. In particular, the version entitled *Articulated Lair* (1986) is "articulated" by means of uprights with casters and hinges, allowing repeated adaptations between the dwelling and the dweller. It is a concealed zone of introspection and protection, so you can "recover and escape" (Bourgeois, quoted in Crone and Schaesberg 2011, 85–86). Evoking the double meaning of the word "wear", Vera seems to show possible ways in which we can lend shape to our sense of self within the pervasive surveillance of everyday life (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Screenshot from Pedro Almodóvar, *The Skin I Live In* (2011) © [El Deseo] 1.23.34

The conspicuous seams in Vera's patchworks thus concretize her self-cohesion through wearing, which is also apparent in the way she wears the immaculate wall of the stark Corbusian-Miesian room. By marking the wall, she attempts to create her own skinspace to inhabit so as to triumph over the binaries of male and female, the natural and the synthetic, and to live with her cyborgian reality. The shadowy area within the panoptic space expands to the point that the wall becomes thoroughly saturated to evoke horror vacui, a fear of empty space that results in the over-marking of visual space. Film and media scholar Braxton Soderman

(2015, 311–312) interprets this phenomenon as stemming from the fear of the unrepresentable, which might reside outside the surface and that constantly threatens to appear within. If Vera is attempting to guard her shadowy space by saturating the white wall, the unrepresentable that she is trying to repel may be revealed through another fictional character who forms a unique relationship with a wall. In Charlotte Perkins Gilman's "The Yellow Wallpaper" (1899), Jane is also locked in a room in an isolated mansion, while she is being "cured". In contrast to Vera's immaculate white wall, Jane's walls are covered in a faded yellow wallpaper with "unblinking", "bulbous" eyes. The monitoring gaze of the panoptical wallpaper reflects the way Jane feels about the identity that her husband and his patriarchal society have inscribed on her (Bak 1994, 45; Gilman 1913). It is only through her association with the wallpaper, by going so far as to become one with it, that Jane establishes an alternative self (Suess 2003, 92). This feminist analysis cannot be easily applied to the situation of Vera, whose gender remains uncertain throughout the film. However, it can be assumed that, as she is incarcerated over a length of time within overwhelming white walls equipped with surveillance cameras, Vera's transgenic skin also becomes panoptic for her—with "thousands of eyes posted everywhere", to borrow Foucault's description of permanent, exhaustive, and omnipresent surveillance.⁹

The tension between voluntary wearing and imposed branding—the relations of power—is thus articulated through various surfaces in Vera's surroundings. If skin-painting or tattooing contributes to the development of social Skin Ego, as pointed out above, the way that Vera turns the immaculate wall into an alternative skinspace can be compared to the way a tattooed person may share agency with their skin. As a technical means of modifying the body, tattooing makes a particular type of subjectivation possible, in that a tattooed body affects the marked person's self and their relationships with others (Gell 1993).¹⁰ The "tattooed" wall can then be regarded as a very different kind of superskin from Ledgard's Gal: the fluid relations between Vera and the wall create a protective hybrid skin, albeit temporarily. In an ontology where the human and the nonhuman are not considered a dichotomy, things may be considered to be powerful (Fahlander 2015, 66). At the same time, the fact that tattoos have also been used to mark the ownership and subjugation of slaves, criminals, and prisoners of war leads me to consider the flawless transgenic skin as a tattooed surface. This contrast between the immaculate tattoo (transgenic skin) and the maculate tattoo (the shadowy wall) reveals an interesting tension between the voluntary and the forced, ownership and submission, human and nonhuman (Fahlander 2015,

52). It also effectively visualizes that the skin as a socially and politically regulated surface that figures various relations of power. As Foucault (1995, 25) stresses, power relations have an immediate hold upon the body: "they invest it, mark it, train it, torture it, force it to carry out tasks, to perform ceremonies, to emit signs". If power relations exist in any social relationship, such a marked body is the substratum of all human subjectivities, as illustrated by the notion of Skin Ego. The gradually expanding shadowy areas on Vera's wall evinces her newly forming Skin Ego, the topography of her new self. Vera's worn space as her strategically extended skin defies the classical ontology that conceives a thing or a person in terms of its closure. She is born out of the surfaces she marks, and her "expanded corporeal space" (Böhme 2000, 16) exemplifies our subjectivities as becomings, the type of existence made strange and highlighted by contemporary technologized bodies.

Conclusion

This essay has considered the various relations of power present in the film *The Skin I Live In* in the context of surveillance capitalism facilitated by biotechnology, (self-)surveillance and mediatized culture. By deploying artificial skin as a cinematic trope that broadly represents the incorporation of technology, the film highlights the skin as a political site through which various power relations may be figured. The asymmetries of knowledge and power brought through by "Big Other" adds another layer to the power relations incorporated in the skin. Although fictitious, the film reveals contemporary anxieties surrounding scientific advancement, the notion of the transhuman, and related ethical concerns, as well as issues of surveillance and its potential effects upon individual freedom. Effectively capturing the condition of being under pervasive surveillance, Vera's transgenic skin prompts us to wonder what kinds of experience are created through our regulated, disciplined and controlled bodies.

Our private spaces no longer provide us with privacy, and the mirrors, scanners, tags, and Wi-Fi hotspots in retail settings can track shoppers in-store to combine the data generated with their online shopping habits, which are then used for digital advertising and product recommendations (CBRE 2018, 17). Smart-city and facial recognition infrastructures can function as the architecture for a permanently alert surveillance state (Warzel 2019). Scott McNealy (quoted in Swisher 2019), the cofounder of Sun Microsystems, informs us that the personal information collected through digital communications is like a "digital tattoo" that is

impossible to expunge. Through Vera's immaculate tattoo (transgenic skin), Almodóvar effectively equates privacy and *freedom*, and this is particularly compelling when so many aspects of our lives depend on technology that exists by exploiting personal data.

While the film reveals how we have become trapped by the mediated surfaces that sustain our interactions (Marcantonio 2015, 50), Vera's resistant strategies present the material skin as a means of situating the self in actuality via a relationship of contiguity. Her creation of an alternative skinspace through her material surroundings seems to reflect Almodóvar's postdigital attitude, which appraises material bodies, disembodied images, and the varying kinds of skin that mediate social encounters. The postdigital opposes the idea of digital progress or the notion of the computer as the universal machine, embracing practical explorations of materials through their imperfections and malfunctions. It sets itself against smart-city projects or self-monitoring practices that feed "big data", such as the quantified self movement (Cramer 2015). Attempts have also arisen to take back control over the access and storage of personal data, such as Tim Berners-Lee's "Solid" ("social linked data") project at MIT, which aims to decentralize the web; or smart clothing that enables the wearers to sell their own data (if they chose to do so) without involving a third party (Peake 2018).

Almodóvar, however, leaves the viewer wondering what will become of Vera: if she will be able to live as multiplicities outside Ledgard's mansion; if the world will let her be free—or indeed, if we are free.

Notes

1. The two main characters in the film highlight multiplicities in the human, challenging the notion of a unique or stable identity. Therefore, I refer to "Vincente/Vera", whose gender and sexual orientation remain uncertain throughout the film, as either "she" or "he", depending on its portrayal in the respective scenes.
2. Although the name "panopticon" suggests vision as the main tool for inspection, Bentham (1995, 36) also suggests that a small tin tube may connect the inspector's lodge with each cell so that even the slightest whisper might be heard by the inspector.
3. The "eye" here is a metaphor for the permanently alert surveillance. Contemporary surveillance operates through multisensory channels, capable of detecting, recording and extracting information across the human sensorium. However, recent privacy concerns around

face recognition technology and drones ("unmanned aerial vehicles") draw attention to the system of visibility. Advanced facial recognition technology utilizing the web of already existing cameras can build an infrastructure for mass surveillance, with a chilling effect on free speech (Chinoy 2019). As a response, in the 2019 Hong Kong protests (against the "Extradition Law Amendment Bill"), the protesters used umbrellas and face masks, and went mainly analog in their movements.

4. Thomas Lemke (2015, 12–13) suggests that through the notions of "technologies of the self" and "government of things", Foucault moved "beyond a concept of biopolitics as limited to the physical and biological existence" to take into account "the interrelatedness and entanglements of men and things, the natural and the artificial, the physical and the moral."
5. In its original context, Peter Osborne's (2015) discussion focuses on transdisciplinarity and the disputes about the rationales of academic disciplines.
6. The French term Foucault uses to designate the processes through which the subject is constituted via power relations is *assujettissement*. Alan Milchman and Alan Rosenberg (2007, 55) emphasizes the importance of acknowledging the active factor in *assujettissement* as "entailing more than relations of domination, as involving the *autonomy*, and the possibility of resistance, of the one who is *assujetti* [subjected] as well." This active factor is restricted in the English translation of *assujettissement* as "subjection" or "subjugation" by different translators. This essay therefore uses "subjectivation", following Milchman and Rosenberg.
7. Eugene Thacker (2003, 74–76) regards Richard Dawkins (along with Hans Moravec, Ray Kurzweil, and Marvin Minsky) as a follower of extropianism, the viewpoint that advanced technologies will augment and advance the human into a posthuman future. Their humanist attitude privileges human's rational thought, self-awareness, and scientific progress without acknowledging the agency of nonhumans that are involved in the transformation of the world. For extropianism, technology is a *transparent* and *value-neutral* tool.
8. See also Lee (2016) for my application of the idea of "common skin" to the human-material relationships in the context of fashion.
9. "[The instrument of surveillance] had to be like a faceless gaze that transformed the whole social body into a field of perception: thousands of eyes posted everywhere, mobile attentions ever on the alert, a long, hierarchized network." (Foucault 1995, 214)

10. Alfred Gell here uses Alan Sheridan's 1979 translation "subjection" (in *Discipline and Punish*) for Foucault's *assujettissement* (see note 6 above).

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